

CURRENT ISSUES IN ORGANIZING THE INDIVIDUAL PREVENTION OF OFFENSES

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Abstract. This article examines the legal and methodological foundations for organizing the individual prevention of offenses, and also provides a comprehensive analysis of the use of digital technologies and innovative forms of resocialization when working with individuals under preventive supervision. Furthermore, it presents scientific and practical proposals aimed at applying foreign experience and curbing criminogenic degradation in order to eliminate systemic problems encountered in practice and increase the effectiveness of the field.

Keywords: individual prevention, prevention inspector, preventive conversation, official warning, social rehabilitation, preventive registration, innovative supervision, resocialization.

In the context of building a new Uzbekistan, ensuring the rule of law in society and raising the legal culture of citizens have become priorities of state policy. Today, the early prevention of offenses yields more effective results than combating their consequences. In particular, individual preventive measures, an important link in the prevention system, are of unparalleled importance in identifying individuals prone to delinquency and exerting targeted educational influence on them.

This activity is aimed not only at punishing the individual but also at eliminating the factors that caused their antisocial behavior, as well as at their social rehabilitation. The individual approaches applied in practice by prevention inspectors serve to ensure stability in society by taking into account the psychological and social characteristics of each citizen. Improving individual prevention mechanisms is a key factor in controlling the criminogenic situation.

The effectiveness of offense prevention largely depends on its solid legal foundation and the systemic connections between its subjects. The legal basis for this activity is regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-371 of May 14, 2014, "On the Prevention of Offenses," which provides a clear legal definition for the concept of individual prevention. According to this law, individual prevention is the activity of bodies and institutions directly implementing the prevention of offenses, aimed at identifying individuals with antisocial behavior, those prone to committing offenses, or those who have committed an offense; maintaining records of them; and exerting an educational influence on them [1].

Kh.D. Abdukhalilov and Sh.Sh. According to the theoretical analysis of Mustafoev, this definition reflects not only the repressive but also the deep socio-pedagogical content of preventive activities [4]. In this legal definition, it is of particular importance that the primary focus of state bodies is not on isolating an individual from society, but on returning them to a socially healthy environment. Thus, maintaining a balance between guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of the individual and eliminating their criminogenic characteristics in the process of individual prevention is a priority legal direction of this activity.

Individual preventive activity is not only a narrow task of law enforcement agencies but also encompasses a wide chain of social institutions. The state has legally established the responsibility of all government agencies and public organizations for the early detection of negative changes in the behavior of every citizen. In this process, a person's life, health, and lifestyle are under constant social control, which is carried out at the mahalla level, which is considered the lowest level of prevention.

According to the scientific views of E.Kh. Norbutaev and D.S. Ochilova, the basis for applying individual prevention must be reliable information indicating an individual's antisocial behavior or tendency toward delinquency [2]. This approach implies that preventive measures must be based not on subjective opinions, but on specific factual data and the real actions of the individual. This procedure prevents prevention inspectors from abusing their powers and ensures personal integrity.

As the central subject of this complex process, the prevention inspector must establish a mechanism for close cooperation with other sectoral services. According to B.A. Mustafakulov and Zh.S. Ruziev, the inspector's activities must be closely linked to the patrol and post service, operational-search units, and juvenile affairs inspectors [3]. In our opinion, such vertical and horizontal cooperation will accelerate the exchange of information about criminogenic persons and ensure the targeted nature of preventive measures. This, in turn, unites the scattered actions of various agencies toward a single goal in crime prevention.

The mechanism of inter-subjective cooperation covers not only government agencies but also non-governmental non-profit organizations and citizens' self-government bodies. Mahalla elders, youth leaders, and women's activists are the closest assistants to the prevention inspector, through whom the most up-to-date information about a person's social environment is obtained. The involvement of every segment of society in preventive activities creates collective immunity in the fight against crime.

According to G. Mikhaleva, the model of individual prevention, along with the unilateral powers of state bodies, should include elements of assistance provided for the social adaptation of the individual [5]. The legal framework should not only consist of restrictions and controls but also include social support measures. It should be noted that the interaction of prevention entities should be aimed not only at monitoring but also at assisting the individual in obtaining employment, education, and medical care.

To achieve the expected result in individual prevention, the differentiation of measures based on an individual's behavior and socio-psychological profile is of methodological priority. The initial and most common form of this process is a preventive interview. According to scientific analysis, the preventive conversation should be aimed at convincing the person to comply with the norms of behavior accepted in society and explaining the legal consequences of the offense [2]. A preventive conversation is not merely formal communication, but a means of psychological influence aimed at penetrating an individual's inner world and changing their criminogenic views. In particular, the effectiveness of this measure directly depends on the communication culture and methodological training of the prevention inspector.

During the preventive interview, the individual's living conditions, family environment, and the reasons prompting them to commit the offense are analyzed. In this case, a differentiated approach means that communication must be established with each person in a separate style based on their level of education, age, and interests. Such individual

communication instills trust in the individual toward state bodies and serves to reduce their level of social danger.

If the preventive interviews conducted do not yield positive results, a more strict methodological measure—a formal warning—will be applied. A formal warning consists of a written explanation to a person that they cannot continue their antisocial behavior and a warning of liability [3]. In our view, this measure serves as a final warning for the individual, formally reinforcing the obligation to comply with legal regulations. This creates a methodological basis for a person to feel responsibility for their actions and to prevent more serious offenses that may occur in the future.

In the process of official notification, there is also a mechanism for notifying the administration at the person's place of work or study. This allows for the use of not only legal but also public influence. When an individual feels that their negative behavior is being discussed in public, it motivates them to change their behavior in a positive direction.

The most complex and systemic measure of individual prevention is social rehabilitation and adaptation. According to G.G. Shikhantsov, the effectiveness of individual prevention is closely linked to the isolation of the individual from the criminogenic environment and their social support (medical, psychological, legal) [7]. Social rehabilitation is not only about controlling the offender but also about creating conditions for them to find a worthy place in society. In this regard, methodologically, the rehabilitation process must offer legal alternatives (work, education, vocational training) that meet the criminogenic needs of the individual.

According to the methodological approach of D.S. Gilmanova, social rehabilitation measures, especially when working with minors, should be carried out by involving them in various sports and creative clubs and meaningfully organizing their free time [9]. An individual approach to the prevention of juvenile delinquency requires taking into account their psychological instability. This requires social adaptation measures to be carried out not merely as an administrative order, but in the form of sincere care and direction.

The aforementioned methodological approaches indicate that individual preventive measures should be applied in a differentiated manner according to the degree of social danger of the individual. At the same time, the individual characteristics of the individual must be at the center of attention at all stages, from the easiest measure (interview) to more complex rehabilitation processes. Such an approach not only curbs crime but also becomes a practical expression of the principles of justice and humanism.

Maintaining preventive records within the individual prevention system is an important tool for establishing systematic control over an individual and preventing their re-offending. According to Article 34 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses," preventive accounting is a set of measures carried out in relation to a specific category of persons for the purpose of their correction and the formation of law-abiding behavior [1]. The uniqueness of this process lies in the fact that it covers not only individuals who have served their sentences but also individuals with antisocial behavior. It should be noted that innovative forms of control should not be aimed at keeping an individual under strict restrictions, but rather at remote and rapid monitoring of their social status.

The role of modern technologies in increasing the efficiency of preventive accounting is invaluable. According to scientific views, the implementation of the "Preventive Accounting" information system today has created an opportunity for inspectors to collect and analyze

personal data in electronic form [3]. In our opinion, the electronic system reduces paperwork and ensures the exchange of information about criminogenic individuals between prevention entities in real time. It follows that innovative forms serve the early prevention of unexpected crimes by responding promptly to every negative change in the personality.

Electronic control systems must be integrated not only with internal affairs bodies but also with other government agencies. For example, collecting information about a person's employment, tax payments, or administrative fines in a single database helps to accurately determine their level of social adaptation. At the same time, the main direction of control remains the curbing of a person's criminogenic activity while adhering to the principles of immunity.

Re-socialization measures are an integral part of control when reintegrating individuals prone to delinquency into society. M.Yu. According to Vodyanaya and K.E. Shilekhin, resocialization is the process of restoring a person's lost social ties and restoring their positive status in society [8]. In our view, innovative resocialization should not be limited to material assistance; it should awaken a sense of need in the individual's consciousness and transform them into a useful member of society. Thus, the use of innovative methods by the public, especially religious and educational organizations, in social adaptation activities increases the effectiveness of spiritual rehabilitation.

Ensuring an individual's employment is one of the most critical factors in the process of social adaptation. According to the scientific views of Yu.V. Gulaev, the presence of a life purpose and employment in an individual prevents the formation of criminogenic motives within them [6]. It is necessary to involve registered individuals in the labor market in an innovative way by training them in the digital economy and modern professions. This serves as a methodological basis for a person to distance themselves from their past and choose a new, legitimate life path.

Innovative forms of social adaptation in working with individuals on preventive records also include constant monitoring of the individual's psychological state. At the same time, the broad involvement of psychologists and sociologists in the prevention system helps eliminate the internal complexes that cause an individual's antisocial behavior. Sustainable results can be achieved not only through punishment and control, but also through the improvement of an individual's spiritual and moral world.

Further improvement of the system of individual crime prevention remains an urgent issue today, both theoretically and practically. According to scientific analysis, one of the main problems encountered in practice is related to the level of psychological and pedagogical training of prevention inspectors. Often, employees use standardized methods when working with a complex contingent [6]. To eliminate this systemic deficiency, it is necessary to instill psychological and pedagogical competencies in personnel during the training stage—that is, to develop the ability to analyze an individual's internal motives. It should be noted that a promising direction for increasing the effectiveness of prevention is the methodological revision of the personnel training system.

M.Yu. According to Vodyanaya and K.E. Shilekhin, another serious problem in the system is the excessive number of preventive subjects and the duplication of tasks between them. For example, when working with persons under administrative supervision or preventive accounting, it is observed that different agencies act independently of each other and sometimes ineffectively [8]. As a scientific and practical solution to this problem, it is advisable

to consolidate all control and support powers into a single coordinating body or create a "Single Preventive Map" through digital management. It follows that long-term prevention must be built not only on a legal restriction but also on a comprehensive plan for which a specific executor is responsible.

Studying foreign experience is important for improving this system. According to research, in countries such as Germany, Denmark, and Switzerland, preventive and administrative supervision measures are considered not only as police supervision but also as a continuation of the criminal execution stage as security measures [8]. The experience of these countries shows that the main emphasis in monitoring an individual is not on punishing them, but on reducing the risk of recidivism through social assistance. In this regard, a promising direction is the further integration of probation and individual prevention institutions in Uzbekistan based on the experience of developed countries.

According to the scientific views of G. Mikhaleva, in order for the priority of the method of persuasion in prevention to give the expected result, it is necessary to create a positive social atmosphere around the person. At the same time, involving not only government agencies but also the private sector and entrepreneurs in prevention (for example, by creating jobs for registered individuals) is a practice widely used abroad [5]. To implement this approach in practice, it is necessary to develop a system for providing legal incentives to social entrepreneurship entities. This accelerates the process of reintegration into society of persons prone to committing offenses.

Systematic analyses show that in practice, there are also legal inconsistencies between the period of preventive registration and a person's criminal record. As a result, even if a person's behavior has fully recovered, they may remain on the record artificially for a long time. To increase the effectiveness of prevention, it is necessary to dynamically determine the deregistration mechanism based on the extinguishing of the individual's criminogenic motives. This allows the inspector to be viewed not only as a supervisor but also as an impartial expert who decides a person's fate.

In conclusion, it should be noted that improving individual prevention requires a systematic approach. The localization of foreign experience, the strengthening of digital monitoring, and the broader use of socio-pedagogical methods in prevention will serve as key factors in the early prevention of crime in the future.

Reforms in the field of individual prevention should not be limited to merely changing legal norms. The main goal is to restore an individual's social connections in society and foster a sincere respect for the law. At the same time, active cooperation between the prevention inspector and public institutions will become the foundation for creating a crime-free environment. Only by combining modern information technologies and humanitarian principles can sustainable positive results be achieved in this field.

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